

THE ESSENCE, PRINCIPLES AND TASKS OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN TEXTILE AND SEWING-KNITTING INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. *This article examines the study of consumer needs in creating a new product, the individuality of the product and its wide differentiation across market segments, i.e. the differentiation of the assortment across market segments, the fact that product competitiveness is not strictly tied to technical standards and norms, i.e. the subjective desires and views of consumers, and the links in the technological chain.*

Keywords: *Enterprise, product, market, assortment, segment, consumer, competition.*

Introduction. Marketing activities are, firstly, the type of work and tasks performed in the field of entrepreneurship; secondly, marketing functions performed to form and reproduce demand, ensuring the company's profit.

Marketing activities are methods used by employees to effectively promote a business in order to increase brand awareness, increase sales, or build relationships with customers.

Marketing activities are the methods companies use to promote their products to existing and new customers.

Marketing activities include a wide range of actions and strategies used by companies to distribute their products, services and brands to target audiences. Entrepreneurship can be shown as an independent type of activity and as a task of integrating the actions of all links in the entrepreneurship and production chain.

Based on the definitions of marketing effectiveness given in the scientific literature, we defined the effectiveness of marketing activities in textile and garment enterprises as the economic result corresponding to a unit of their marketing costs. By this we mean measures aimed at increasing effectiveness, intensifying marketing activities, and increasing their effectiveness.

Analysis of literature on the topic. An analysis of the existing literature on marketing shows the need to improve modern marketing principles, brand promotion methods and a flexible approach to consumer requirements. In his textbook on marketing strategies, the expert R. Ibragimov states the following: "Marketing strategy is understood as the use of a model of the principles of the enterprise's behavior in the market, established for a certain period of time. With its help, the enterprise seeks to ensure its success." Many economists have been involved in the development and implementation of marketing strategies. Among them are such famous scientists as F. Kotler, David Aaker, Clayton Christensen, Seth Godin, Kevin Keller, Byron Sharp, and Jay Bayer.

While the research conducted in the field of marketing in our country for many years is based on national characteristics, it is also necessary to recognize the scientists who have made a significant contribution to the development of marketing theory. These include R. Ibragimov,

YO.Abdullaev, A.Saliev, M.Sharifkhodjaev, D.Rakhimova, Sh.Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh.Musayeva and others..

Research methodology. The study used a systematic approach, marketing analysis, benchmarking, and digital metrics. Mass surveillance methods were used to collect and analyze data from social media platforms.

Analysis and results. Based on the chosen field, goals and tasks of the article, we offer the following definition: the marketing activity of a textile and sewing-knitting enterprise is the activity of implementing methods and means of marketing functions aimed at satisfying the needs of consumers in order to create a competitive advantage in a certain type and segment of the market and ensure long-term competitiveness.

Apparently, marketing in textile enterprises The diversity of the content, directions and means of marketing activity has led to the lack of a single approach to its definition and the fact that scientists have made unique proposals for this complex type of activity. Debates among scientists continue not only about the definition of marketing activities in textile enterprises, but also about its composition. Most scientists consider marketing activities to be identical with marketing tasks, that is, they consider them to consist of marketing research, marketing policies, marketing strategy, promotion and marketing services. Some scientists consider marketing activities to consist of two groups, namely strategic and operational marketing. The literature also presents ideas for separating the structure of marketing activities from the point of view of marketing functions (market research, planning, analytical, sales, and others).

Considering the relevance and complexity of the problem for the industry, based on the purpose, tasks and limitations of the thesis in our research in the textile and sewing-knitting industry we intended to use it in the following order when solving it (Fig. 1).

Based on this scheme, it can be seen that scientific research needs to be conducted in several directions:

What are the characteristics of enterprises in the textile and sewing-knitting industry and their role in the economic policy of our country?

What is the uniqueness of marketing activities in these enterprises?

What is the role of textile and sewing-knitting industry marketing activities in the regional economy?

What are the common and different aspects of marketing activities of textile and sewing-knitting enterprises?

What are the scientific bases of improving marketing activities in textile and sewing-knitting enterprises?

To answer the above questions, the characteristics of marketing activities in the industry are primarily related to the characteristics of the product being produced in the consumer market. These characteristics include:

- The impact of fashion on the formation of consumer needs and the shortness of the product's life cycle in the market due to its influence;
- The influence of public opinion on a consumer's purchasing decision, that is, the manufacturer's idea is only confirmed or refuted in the sales floor;
- The need to create a positive attitude among consumers about a product before it is released to the market. When creating a new product, it is necessary to study the needs of consumers and prepare them accordingly to consume the new product.

- The individuality of the product and its wide differentiation by market segments, that is, the differentiation of the assortment by market segments. For example, the segments of the world textile market include the final consumer market, home textile products, and technical textile products;
- Orientation of the product to a certain type of market in terms of useful properties and usefulness, that is, in most cases, this feature determines the target market of the enterprise (broad consumer market, enterprise market, public procurement market, etc.);
- Product competitiveness is not strictly connected to technical standards and norms, that is, it is influenced by the subjective wishes and views of consumers.

Figure 1. Scientific research scheme for improvement of marketing activity in textile and sewing-knitting industry.

On the other hand, the influence of production factors on the marketing of the textile and garment-knitting industry is of great importance for revealing its content. We believe that these factors can include the following.

1. Textile and garment enterprises form links in a single technological chain. Starting from the spinning of natural and artificial fibers to the creation of clothing or other consumer products, enterprises form a holistic system through mutual relations. The marketing activities of an individual enterprise are determined by its place in this system;

2. The strategic importance of raw materials used in the textile and garment industry. Cotton fibers serve as the main raw material for textile enterprises in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Most of the cotton, cocoons, and wool raw materials produced in our country are intended for textile and garment enterprises. In this regard, restrictions on the sources of raw materials create specific forms

of competition between enterprises. Enterprises struggle not only for dominance in segments of the consumer market, but also for dominance in the raw material market.

3. The socio-political importance of the textile and garment industry in the economy of Uzbekistan. The natural and geopolitical conditions of our country make the role of the textile industry in employment, welfare, and export potential of the population a priority, given the deep understanding of the state support strategy for enterprises. This, in turn, has a significant impact on the marketing activities of enterprises.

As a result of the research, we have identified specific characteristics of textile and garment enterprises, depending on the products they produce and their place in the processing chain, as a factor determining marketing activities. According to this characteristic, it is appropriate to divide textile and garment enterprises into the following groups: yarn spinning enterprises (YE), textile enterprises (T), garment and garment enterprises (TT). We have determined that the enterprises included in the group have generalizing characteristics related to marketing (1-table).

1-table.

Marketing features of textile and sewing-knitting enterprises.*

	spinning yarn(IC)	Textiles (T)	sewing-knitting and clothing (TT)
Product feature	are purchased as raw materials in production	Production raw materials (fabric, ...) products for the manufacturing industry, products for the consumer market (carpets, floor coverings)	A wide range of consumer goods, fashionable design, customization
Enterprise feature	Narrow specialization, technology suitable for raw materials, integration with T enterprises	wide range of products, various technological lines, integration with IC enterprises	A wide range of products, cutting-edge technology, design and experimental workshops
Type of sales market	V2V, international market	V2V, V2S. V2G, international market	V2S. V2G, international market
Type of shopping market	agrocluster	the front link of the technological chain, the V2V market	IK and T enterprises, commodity exchange
Marketing strategy	product improvement	improvement of production, improvement of product quality, expansion of the consumer market	Consumer-oriented marketing, social marketing, global marketing.
Product policy	adaptation to technical standards	compliance with technical norms and	Following fashion and design

		standards, design and appearance	
Pricing policy	costs plus profit, competition- price	cost plus profit, stock prices, competition-price	Competition – price
Merchandise Movement Policy	closed channels	Semi-closed and open channels	Open, multi-stage channels
Communication policy	increasing the number of regular customers, direct marketing, exhibition, advertising	Introducing the enterprise to the market, all types of advertising, direct marketing,	Customer attraction, sales promotion, advertising,
Marketing Service Policy	Knowledge of pre-enterprise and post-enterprise chain link, contracting skills, quality standards	Improving product quality, expanding the market, promoting promotion channels, accelerating sales, improving marketing	Studying consumers, adapting the assortment to demand, stimulating the movement channels, accelerating sales, improving marketing
Marketing research	Studying the textile industry market, studying demand for products, monitoring scientific and technical news and innovations; studying the capabilities and characteristics of agroclusters	Market analysis, customer research, segmentation, product research, market monitoring, fashion news monitoring	Market analysis, customer research, segmentation, product research, market monitoring, fashion news monitoring

*-compiled by the author

The specialization of textile and sewing-knitting enterprises by type of market serves as a factor determining the marketing characteristics. We have already noted that one of the distinctive features of textile products is its special orientation. The narrow specialization of the enterprise mainly serves as a target orientation of its activities for one market. Usually this is the consumer market (B2C), the market of industrial enterprises (B2B), the market of government orders (B2G) and international markets. Then the methods, tools and programs of marketing activities are tailored to this market.

The content of the marketing activities of textile and sewing and knitting enterprises is greatly influenced by the position of the enterprise in the market. According to the theory of strategic marketing, the competitors of enterprises mainly belong to one strategic group, that is, the closest competitors should be very close to each other in terms of product type, sales volume, attention to market segments, and other characteristics..

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